

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.04.2023.1
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10058126
 UDC: 378.147+316.422
 JEL: I29

DIGITAL LEARNING TOOLS AS A MEANS OF UKRAINIAN VETERANS' READAPTATION TO SOCIAL LIFE

ЦИФРОВІ ІНСТРУМЕНТИ НАВЧАННЯ ЯК ЗАСІБ РЕАДАПТАЦІЇ УКРАЇНСЬКИХ ВЕТЕРАНІВ ДО СУСПІЛЬНОГО ЖИТТЯ

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Received 20.08.2023

Балан О.С., Шепель М.С., Морріс К. Цифрові інструменти навчання як засіб реадптації українських ветеранів до суспільного життя. Оглядова стаття.

Статтю присвячено використанню цифрових інструментів навчання як засобу реадптації українських ветеранів до суспільного життя. Метою статті виступило дослідити важливість цифрових інструментів навчання як засобу реадптації українських ветеранів до суспільного життя та надати рекомендації щодо їх використання у навчальному процесі. Зроблено аналіз літератури щодо адаптації ветеранів, використанню цифрових інструментів у навчанні. Результати проведеного авторами анкетування серед українських ветеранів та військовослужбовців у рамках програми подвійних грантів УК-Ukraine twinning grants scheme (Проект UUT06 «Цифровізація як засіб підвищення доступності вищої освіти для Українських ветеранів») показало, що ветерани та військовослужбовці готові до отримання нової освіти, але мають досить низький рівень обізнаності щодо цифрових інструментів навчання. Авторами зазначено, що цифрові інструменти навчання можуть принести користь у процесі реадптації ветеранів до суспільного життя.

Ключові слова: цифрові інструменти навчання, адаптація, реадптація, суспільне життя, ветеран, Україна

Balan O.S., Shepel M.Ye., Morris Ch. Digital Learning Tools as a Means of Ukrainian Veterans' Readaptation to Social Life. Review article.

The article is dedicated to digital learning tools application as a means of readapting Ukrainian veterans to social life. The aim of the article is to investigate the importance of digital learning tools as a means of readapting Ukrainian veterans to social life and to provide recommendations for their application in the educational process. References on veterans' adaptation, applying digital tools in education have been analysed. The results of a survey conducted by the authors among Ukrainian veterans and military personnel within the framework of the UK-Ukraine twinning grants scheme (Project UUT06 "Digitisation as a means of improving accessibility of Higher Education to Ukrainian veterans") have shown that the veterans and military personnel are ready to get a new education, but have rather low level of digital learning tools awareness. The authors note that digital learning tools can be beneficial in the process of the veterans' readaptation to social life.

Keywords: digital learning tools, adaptation, readaptation, social life, a veteran, Ukraine

Since 2014 Ukrainian society has faced previously unknown challenges after the beginning of the war in the east of our country. According to the data of the Ministry of Veterans Affairs of Ukraine [1], there are currently 670 458 combatants and war veterans in Ukraine, 30 650 of which are from the Odesa region. One of the main challenges caused by the war for Ukrainian society is the veterans' full adaptation to civilian life, as it is known that during this period there is a change of roles in society in general, and in families in particular. The physical and psychological consequences of being at the frontline in every second of danger leave their consequences. According to the Twentieth National Survey in war conditions, conducted by the "Rating" Sociological Group on the initiative of the "Ukrainian Veterans Fund", the Ministry of Veterans Affairs of Ukraine on 14-16 January 2023, 47% of the respondents noted that among their relatives and friends, there were those who took participation in military operations on the territory of Ukraine, from 2014 to 2021. 63% of the respondents had among their loved ones those who fought or have been fighting at the frontline, starting from 24 February 2022. Also, according to the study, conflicts in the family, lack of work, and abuse of alcohol or drugs are key problems that veterans of the Russian-Ukrainian war are likely to face after returning home. More than 50% of respondents had the same viewpoint. Among the main problems that veterans face most often, the relative majority identified psychological disorders – 40%. From 23%

to 29% consider the main problems to be difficulties with benefits registration, job search, receiving medical care, and society's misunderstanding. Conflicts with loved ones and family or alcohol or drug addiction were mentioned by 14% of the respondents as problems of veterans [2]. In this regard, it is important to think about building a system of the veterans' adaptation in war and post-war times, as after demobilization, they face challenges related to the lack of a built-in system of physical and psychological recovery, resocialization, education and retraining, access to the public administration system, and financial support.

Analysis of recent research and publications

To date, there is no generally accepted definition or process of servicemen's social adaptation, which is equally used and recognized both in domestic and foreign scientific literature. Among Ukrainian scholars, the prevailing understanding of the adaptation process is primarily adjustment to labour market conditions with the help of professional retraining. A. Krasylshchikov [3], Ye. Abramov [4], O. Buryak and M. Ginevskiy [5] dedicated their studies to various aspects of former military personnel employment. The issues of financial support for social adaptation were investigated by T. Vdovichenko [6].

We should also note the empirical base expansion. Recently, several national studies have been conducted. The first was conducted in 2016 by the sociologists of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv on the initiative of the Fund of War Veterans and ATO Participants, its results are presented in a number of publications [7, 8]. The "Ukrainian Association of Specialists in Overcoming the Psychotraumatic Events Consequences" with the support of the "Renaissance" International Foundation conducted the study "Psychological and Social Assistance through the ATO Veterans' Eyes" [9].

In February 2022, a nationwide survey "Veterans' Reintegration in Ukraine" was published. It was developed as a part of the project "Strengthening the Communities Resilience through Veteran's Socio-Economic Support", financed by the European Union. The qualitative and quantitative components of the study were conducted in June – October 2021 in 24 regions of Ukraine and the city of Kyiv by surveying 4,286 veterans included in the survey sample. In addition to the above sample, 40 respondents, including veterans, their family members, and other key respondents, participated in in-depth interviews [10].

The works of foreign scholars who dedicated their studies to veterans' social adaptation are also of great importance. Thus, the American scientists K. Elnitsky, M. Fisher and K. Blevins [11] clarified various concepts of servicemen's social adaptation and highlighted the factors of their choice in real life. The Bulgarian researchers V. Terziev and S. Dimitrova focused their attention on various models of social adaptation of military personnel and factors affecting the institutionalization level of this process [12]. L. Cooper, N. Caddick, L. Gaudier, A. Cooper,

and M. Fosse [13] devoted their study to the cultural aspects of the social adaptation of military personnel, where they revealed the influence of such factors as gender and identity. E. Jones [14] convincingly demonstrated that approaches to social adaptation and even physical and psychological disorders associated with military service have a strong cultural basis. An empirical study by the American R. Morin [15] is devoted to the success factors of the social adaptation process. Much attention in foreign literature is paid to the study and justification of approaches that would allow overcoming the limitations of the existing system of social adaptation. In particular, the research of R. Cornum, M. Matthews, and M. Seligman [16] is devoted to proactive methods.

Education is a part of the cultural aspect of social adaptation. Nowadays digitisation plays an important role in education development and improvement. Such scientists as V. Areshonkov [17], O. Buynytska, L. Varchenko-Trotsenko, B. Hrytselyak [18], S Karp-liuk [19], V. Kremen, V. Bykov, O. Lyashenk, S. Litvynov, V. Lugovoi, Y. Malyovana, O. Pinchuk, O. Topuzov [20], P. Mertala [21], J.T. Schmidt and M. Tang [22], V.F. Crittentent, I.K. Bylia, V. Lovely [26] dedicated their studies to the problems of digitisation.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Even in these difficult conditions, education remains an important component of Ukraine's security and stability. The ability to apply various platforms, consciously consume information, and critical thinking are strategic for the country's development, especially in war conditions.

In the period of war, the servicemen who have been wounded and released from military service return to peaceful life. When the war ends, a large number of servicemen will be demobilized and the issue of facilitating their adaptation to peaceful life will arise. We believe that education and professional development will play a key role in the post-war reconstruction of Ukrainian territories and the veterans' adaptation to changes in technology and the labour market. And our society should do everything not to have a "lost generation" as it was after World War I.

The aim of the article is to study the importance of learning digital tools in veterans' social readaptation to civil life and give recommendations on their application.

The main part

The very concept of social adaptation does not have a consensus on its application, which would adequately reflect the process of servicemen's returning to civilian life. Other terms that reflect social adaptation are used in Ukraine and abroad, such as reintegration, transition, readaptation, and integration into the community.

Thus, according to the study data on the evaluation of the impact of military experience and reintegration conducted among the ATO participants in 2021, it showed the following results: only on the line of fire do people understand what is important

and what is not (86%), participation in military operations forever changed the respondent's life (84%), veterans can only be understood by those who fought (83%), in peaceful life the rights of veterans are violated (75%). A survey among veterans regarding the assessment of veterans' ability to influence changes in the community (South), that is, to be integrated into community life, showed the following: fully agree – 18%, agree – 15%, rather agree – 28%, disagree – 33%, completely do not agree – 7%. When evaluating fundamental values by veterans – the share of those who noted the importance of various values in their lives (South) the following data were obtained – family (89%), personal independence (60%), friends (72%), free time (leisure) (63%), work (65%), education (36%), religion (12%), social activities (15%), politics (14%) [10].

In our opinion, the above-mentioned fundamental values influence the veterans' adaptation to civilian life. The process of veterans' adaptation to civilian life can be accompanied by a change in professional activity, the acquisition of new knowledge, abilities and skills. In this case, the Code of Labor Laws of Ukraine [24], which defines the legal principles and guarantees of Ukraine's citizens exercising the right to manage their abilities for productive and creative work, becomes important.

When changing professional activity, there is an adaptation to the new activity (professional adaptation) and to the environment, a new team (social adaptation). Social and professional adaptation should be considered interrelated. Social adaptation

helps in conducting an analysis of the life situation, determining the main problems, ways to solve them; providing information on issues of the population' social protection; training, formation and development of social skills and abilities; assistance in strengthening/restoring family and socially beneficial ties, organization of daytime employment and leisure time.

At the same time, individuals have the right to social and professional adaptation. Thus, the professional adaptation of physically challenged people as a result of the war is organized in accordance with the recommendations of the medical and social expert commission, defined in the individual rehabilitation programme. In the case when such persons need special conditions for professional training, taking into account individual rehabilitation programmes, adapted training places, their professional adaptation is organized in institutions and rehabilitation centres where appropriate conditions have been created. A person can get either a new profession or improve already skills obtained.

Individuals' (in our case veterans') vocational training can be implemented in full-time, evening (shift), part-time, distance, external forms of training, with or without separation from production, and according to individual training plans.

The term of a person's professional training is determined by work training plans, work training programmes and educational programmes in accordance with the legislation. In the case of the organization of training in labour professions, the term may not exceed 12 months.

Table 1. The Legislative Basis for Education Digitisation Development

Year	Document title	Aim
2018	Regulations on the National Educational Electronic Platform [25]	E-learning development, creation electronic educational resources and formation, digital competencies formation of the educational process participants
2018	Regulations on the Electronic Textbook [26]	
2019	Regulations on Electronic Educational Resources [27]	
2021	Description of of digital competences framework of Ukraine's citizens [28]	
Up to 2023	Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the Sustainable Development Goals of Ukraine for the period up to 2030 [29]	
By the years of creation	Standards of higher education specialties [30]	

Source: compiled by authors on materials [25-30]

In addition to the above-mentioned documents, which are aimed at stimulating digital transformations in the education system, the Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine [31] ("Dii. Digital Education" Project) [32], the Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine [33], as well as numerous public organizations.

Today, many modern tools are available to educators, in particular, ubiquitous communication – Skype, Microsoft Teams, Google Meets and Zoom.

In addition to the recognized tools, the distance learning implementation is also carried out by the of education digitisation tools, which for greater clarity are presented in the form of Table 2.

Table 2 Education Digitisation Tools

General	Aim	Example
1	2	3
Platforms for online learning	You can study online using video lessons, interactive tasks, and have the support of a specialist through chats	Coursera, MOU (Maidan Open University), Prometheus, EDX, Udacity, Udeya, Edera, Khan Academy, etc
Learning management systems	Teachers can provide their material and monitor students' activity	Moodle, Canvas Network, Blackboard

Continuation of Table 2

1	2	3
Video conferences and webinars	Allow you to meet in real-time	Zoom, Skype, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams
Platforms for information storage	Cloud storage	Google Docs, Google Class, Dropbox, Onedrive
Mobile apps for training, interactive simulators	For non-stop training	Duolingo, Memrise, Rosetta Stone
Augmented and virtual reality tools	Enable the creation of immersive learning experiences that enhance understanding of complex concepts and processes	Google Expeditions, Oculus Rift, HTC Vive
Tools for recording activity	Notice boards, informing students	Miro, Trello, Notion
Game educational tools	Learning through game	Kahoot!, Quizlet

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Digitisation makes the educational process more mobile, flexible, personalized and differentiated. It significantly affects the education content, methods, means and technologies of education, organisational forms of education and educational and cognitive activities management, which leads to changes in students' and teachers activities. Individual and group work combination, as well as the time limitlessness of learning frees up time to provide feedback, the opportunity to design individual educational routes for students and teachers, practically implement the idea of continuous education or lifelong education. It is digital tools that create positive and safe conditions for the veterans' full return to civilian life. Our

As our piece of research is dedicated to education digitisation tools application in Ukrainian veterans'

social readaptation to civil life, we wanted to know the veterans and servicemen's opinion about digitisation tools in education.

In the framework of UK-Ukraine Twinning Grants Scheme Project UUT06 "Digitisation as a means of improving accessibility of Higher Education to Ukrainian veterans" we have conducted the poll dedicated to veterans' retraining and readaptation using digital learning tools.

The respondents' education was of great importance. 45.5% of respondents had completed secondary special education, 19.2% were Bachelors, 12.1% had only secondary education, 10.1% were Masters, and 9.6% were students of educational institutions. For greater clarity, we present the data in the form of Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Respondents' Level of Education at the Time of Mobilization

Source: the authors' own elaboration

It was interesting to look at the respondents' survey regarding post-mobilization plans. Thus, after the war, 36.4% of respondents wanted to return to their old job, 18.2% of the respondents wanted to remain in the military, 17.7% wanted to open their own business, 14.1% wanted to get a new specialty, and 8.6% wanted to work in the community in public authorities, etc. (Figure 2).

After the demobilization, veterans may need help finding new jobs or career opportunities, especially if they have been in a combat zone for a long time. This

may include a variety of support programs for employment, professional development and training.

The veteran's education is an important component of the adaptation process to life after returning from the hostilities zone. So, training veterans in digital technologies is especially important, as they are necessary for most professions and enable industry development. Training can also help the veterans to maintain their level of professional skills, which in turn provides them with a better chance of employment and career advancement.

Training and retraining can help the veterans acquire new knowledge and skills, which in turn will provide them with the opportunity to develop themselves as

professionals. Learning new skills and knowledge can be part of the rehabilitation process that helps the veterans to return to normal life after war.

Figure 2. The Respondents' Plans after Demobilization
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

Let's have a look at the survey results. Thus, 37.2% of the respondents wanted to develop themselves in their specialties, 10.2 % wanted to develop themselves in military education, 21.2% wanted to build their own business in the field of

trade, 9.9% in the field of public administration, 9.1% wanted to build their business in the field of production, 5,8 % wanted to build their business in the field of IT, 3,3% wanted to be engaged in social activities etc. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Areas, Where the Respondents Want to Develop Themselves
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

So, we can conclude, that the demand for improving public management skills, building one's own business in the field of trade and production, and managing a public organization after the war has great prospects for growth. And that's why it's so important to build any learning engagement strategies with the help of digital technologies.

Regarding the skills that the respondents would like to improve and develop, we have received the following data. According to our research, 20.0% of respondents would like to master public speaking skills, 19.3% – conflict management skills, 18.8% – effective communication skills, 15.4% – project management skills, 11.3% – their own business organization, running a private enterprise, 9.2% –

emotions regulation, public organization management. The results are presented in Figure 4.

Thus, we can see that more than half of the respondents want to readapt to a social peaceful life.

We were also interested in what principles the respondents would choose an institution of higher education (HEI) for further education. So, 26.8% of the respondents were interested in free education, 24.9% were oriented towards the availability of a specialty of interest, 17.2% were guided by the institution's convenient location (close to the place of residence), 10.3% were guided by the brothers in arms' recommendations, 9.1% wanted to get an education abroad (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Skills that the Respondents Would Like to Improve
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

Figure 5. According to What Principles the Respondents Will Choose a Higher Education Institution (HEI) for Further Education
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

As our survey is dedicated to the veterans' adaption with digital learning tools, we asked the veterans where it is better to place information about educational opportunities, the following data were received. Thus, 31.6% chose "Chat-bot for veterans" to receive information. 23.2% considered it effective

to receive information through military commissars, 19.8% – through military units, 16.2% – through employment centres, 6.3% – saw the sense in imparting information in medical institutions (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The Best Place to Post Information about Educational Opportunities
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

Our survey has shown that the most popular is the request for a short-term online study with the acquisition of a new specialty 48%, 21.2% were ready to join the new training face-to-face, with a gap from

work, 11.6% were ready to receive a Master's degree within 1.5-2 years, 9.1% were ready to study for 4-6 years, 8.1% were ready to receive a second education within 2,5-3 years (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Time-Effective Forms of Education

Source: the authors' own elaboration

As for online and offline format we have received the following data. 50% of respondents considered it effective to study online from a place convenient for them, 32.3% prefer hybrid formats, 16.7% – spoke in favour of physical presence with the teacher in the

same room. In addition, a question was raised regarding soft skills development, which are important in any area and make a university graduate more self-confident and more effective when communicating with people (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Forms of education that are effective in the ways of organizing education

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Analyzing the respondents' responses dedicated to effective teaching methods (according to the respondents) we see the following results: giving lectures (online and offline) (7.2%), making a presentation with its further spread among students, (8.6%), using mobile apps during practical classes (9.5%), placing video lessons for free watching, and during classes conduct live discussion with on topic and its practical application (the "Flip-up Class" technique) (15.3%), under the HEI programme to develop online courses, to give students access to them and to take into account estimations for their taking (5.4%), teachers give course materials in advance, questions for examination and organize

consultations (6.5%), teachers are able to combine online and offline formats so that everyone is heard and visible (6.8%), the department staff regularly hold thematic practical conferences (3.3%), to create virtual libraries where the necessary literature is presented as fully as possible (5.3%), existing interactive platform for teachers and students' communication (3.1%), interactive training simulators application for mastering practical skills (7.3%), project activity organization (individually, in pairs, small groups) (6.2%), organizing effective practice for students of any study mode (6.2%), creating online games, role playing games, simulations (online and offline) (online and offline) (8.4%), other (0.9%).

Figure 9. Effective Teaching Methods according to the Respondents

Source: the authors' own elaboration

We wanted to know the level of familiarity with learning platforms. It has shown a negative result. Unfortunately, the majority of respondents are not

familiar with any platform (54.7%). Among the most common, they named Prometheus (15.9%), Udemy (11.9%), and Coursera (6.5%) (Figure 10).

Figure 10. The Level of Familiarity with Learning Platforms

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The level of respondents' familiarity with learning management systems (79.6%) is critical. Only 10.5%

of respondents were familiar with Moodle, 7.7% with Canvas Network, as it is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. The Level of Familiarity with Learning Management Systems

Source: the authors' own elaboration

As for videoconferencing tools that can be used in education the respondents named Zoom (38.7%), Skype (30.4%), and Google Meet (16.4%). Other programmes had a small percentage among the respondents. Discord and Slack were not included in

the questionnaire but were named by the respondents as the ones they know and use (Figure 12).

The respondents identified Google Docs (37%) and Dropbox (24%) as the most common platforms for storing information (Figure 13).

Figure 12. The Level of Familiarity with Video Conferencing Platforms
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

Figure 13. The Level of Familiarity with Information Storage Platforms
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

To our great sorrow, the majority of respondents are not familiar with mobile apps that can be used in the learning process (60.3%). The Duolingo application (25.2%) was the most famous among the respondents (Figure 14).

Unfortunately, the critical majority of respondents were not familiar with tools for recording individual or group work performance (76.4%) (Figure 15).

Unfortunately, a critical number of respondents was unfamiliar with digital gaming tools (71.2%) (Figure 16).

Figure 14. Level of familiarity with mobile applications
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

Figure 15. The Level of Familiarity with tools for fixing developments
Source: the authors' own elaboration

Figure 16. The Level of Familiarity with Gaming Digital Tools
Source: the authors' own elaboration

Summarizing this component of the study, we see a critical level of practice in using various digital educational tools. Among the reasons, we can identify the following:

- teachers do not suggest using it and students do not use it,
- lack of information about alternative digital tools, the tendency to use those that are used to, even if their capabilities are limited.

Digital learning tools have become a part of the modern education. They were started to be used during the COVID-19 pandemic. These tools give great opportunities for teachers and students in the education process: they can interact from any point of the world, and collaborate together when creating different projects.

As for the veteran's readaptation to social life digital learning tools can be a very powerful source for self-development, a kind of distraction from dark thoughts. Having experience in working with digital learning tools we would like to give recommendations for their application:

- Use only one platform for conducting lectures/practical classes (Moodle, Google Classroom, Microsoft Teams);
- Before using the above-mentioned platforms, provide learners with a short introductory course.

- Don't overload your learners with different apps, as a big part of the veterans may have problems with concentration.
- Use instant messaging (Viber, Telegram, Whatsapp) with your learners for quick exchange of information.
- Tell your students about different learning platforms as additional materials to your course.

Conclusions

Education, retraining, and advanced training are some of the most important components of successful adaptation to civilian life. Despite the fact that the Ministry of Education and Science has developed a system of educational support for war veterans and participants in hostilities during the recruitment campaign and during the training period, we believe that the society has not developed a system for forming motivation to study, raising the level of education and retraining.

The veterans' survey has shown a positive forecast regarding the request for additional education, satisfaction with their specialty and the desire to undergo additional professional development, obtaining a new specialty, but a very low percentage included it in their plans.

Digital tools can be useful in the process of veterans' adaptation to social life. In order to realize

this goal, it is important to understand all the advantages and disadvantages of individual tools; create certain resources about educational opportunities for veterans and launch an information campaign regarding access to these resources for

veterans; monitor the veterans' requests and create additional digital tools; to realize that the veterans need communication, inclusion, activity, work in small groups, communication as equals for full-fledged social adaptation.

Abstract

Ukrainian society has faced previously unknown challenges after the beginning of the war in the east of our country in 2014. The data of the Ministry of Veterans Affairs of Ukraine shows that there are currently 670 458 combatants and war veterans in Ukraine, 30 650 of which are from the Odesa region. One of the main challenges caused by the war for Ukrainian society is the veterans' full adaptation to civilian life. It is known that during this period there is a change of roles in society in general, and in families in particular. In our opinion, one of the main challenges caused by the war for Ukrainian society is the veterans' full adaptation to civilian life. According to the Twentieth National Survey in war conditions, conducted by "Rating" Sociological Group on the initiative of the "Ukrainian Veterans Fund", the Ministry of Veterans Affairs of Ukraine on 14-16 January 2023, problems that veterans face most often, the relative majority identified psychological disorders – 40%, from 23% to 29% consider the main problems to be difficulties with benefits registration, job search, receiving medical care, and society's misunderstanding, conflicts with loved ones and family or alcohol or drug addiction were mentioned by 14% of the respondents as the veterans' problems. In this regard, it is important to think about building a system of the veterans's adaptation during the war and post-war times.

Even in these difficult conditions, education remains an important component of the country's security and stability. The ability to apply various platforms, consciously consume information, and critical thinking are strategic for the country's development, especially in war conditions.

In the period of war, servicemen who have been wounded and released from military service return to peaceful life. When the war ends, a large number of servicemen will be demobilized and the issue of facilitating their adaptation to peaceful life will arise. We believe that education and professional development will play a key role in the post-war reconstruction of Ukrainian territories and the veterans' adaptation to changes in technology and the labour market. And our society should do everything not to have a "lost generation" as it was after World War I.

The aim of the article is to investigate the importance of learning digital tools in veterans' social readaptation to civil life and give recommendations on their application.

Despite the fact that the Ministry of Education and Science has developed a system of educational support for war veterans and combatants during the recruitment campaign and during the training period, we believe that the society has not developed a system for forming motivation to study, raising the level of education and retraining.

The veterans' survey has shown a positive forecast regarding the request for additional education, satisfaction with their specialty and the desire to undergo additional professional development, obtaining a new specialty, but a very low percentage included it in their plans.

Digital tools can be useful in the process of veterans' adaptation to social life. In order to realize this goal, it is important to understand all the advantages and disadvantages of individual tools; create certain resources about educational opportunities for veterans and launch an information campaign regarding access to these resources for veterans; monitor the veterans' requests and create additional digital tools; to realize that the veterans need communication, inclusion, activity, work in small groups, communication as equals for full-fledged social adaptation.

Список літератури:

1. Аналітична інформація за даними Міністерства у справах ветеранів України [Електронний ресурс]: Міністерство у справах ветеранів України. – Режим доступу: <https://data.mva.gov.ua>.
2. Двадцять загальнонаціональне опитування. Образ ветеранів в українському суспільстві (14-16 січня 2023) [Електронний ресурс] // Соціологічна група «Рейтинг» – Режим доступу: bit.ly/46n92wQ.
3. Красильщиков А.Л. Соціальна адаптація звільнених у запас військовослужбовців (проблеми та досвід їх вирішення в Україні та зарубіжних країнах) / А.Л. Красильщиков // Демографія та соціальна економіка – 2005. – № 2. – С. 117-125.
4. Абрамов С.В. Адаптація військовослужбовців, звільнених в запас як інструмент забезпечення їх конкурентоспроможності на ринку праці [Текст] С.В. Абрамов // Економіка і організація управління, 2016. – №2 (22). – С. 259-265.
5. Буряк О.О. Соціальна адаптація армії України до нових умов існування / О.О. Буряк, М.І. Гіневський // Збірник наукових праць Харківського національного університету Повітряних Сил. – 2014. – № 4(41). – С. 160-166.
6. Тарас Вдовиченко. Соціальна та професійна адаптація звільнених військовослужбовців як об'єкт фінансового забезпечення / Т. Вдовиченко // Світ фінансів. – 2017. № 1 (50). – С. 166-180.

7. Берездецька Л. Особливості користування державними програмами демобілізованими учасниками АТО в українському суспільстві [Текст] / Л. Берездецька // Вісник НТУУ «КПІ». Політологія. Соціологія. Право. – 2016. – Випуск 1/2 (29-30) – С. 30-38.
8. Харченко О., Мраморова О. Проблеми ветеранів антитерористичної операції на сході України [Текст] / О. Харченко, О. Мраморова // Вісник ХНУ імені В. Н. Каразіна. Серія «Соціологічні дослідження сучасного суспільства: методологія, теорія, методи». – 2016. – Том 37 – С. 115-124.
9. Психологічна та соціальна допомога очима ветеранів АТО [Електронний ресурс]: (Дослідження) / МБФ «Відродження, Психологічна кризова служба України. – 2016 – Режим доступу: bit.ly/3tjQkYm.
10. Реінтеграція ветеранів в Україні. Національне опитування. Київ: MOM, Прямуюємо разом, М-во у справах ветеранів України, 2022. 58 с. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: bit.ly/46qKh3f.
11. Elnitsky C.A. Military Service Member and Veteran Reintegration: A Conceptual Analysis, Unified Definition, and Key Domains [Електронний ресурс] / Christine A. Elnitsky, Michael P. Fisher, Cara L. Blevins // *Frontiers in Psychology*. – 2017. – Т. 8. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00369.
12. Terziev V.A New View on Social Adaptation of the Military, Discharged from Military Service in Bulgaria / V. Terziev, S. Dimitrova // *European Scientific Journal*. – 2014. – Vol. 2. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://eujournal.org/index.php/esj/article/viewFile/4792/4608>.
13. Transition from the Military Into Civilian Life [Електронний ресурс] / Linda Cooper [та ін.] // *Armed Forces & Society*. – 2016. – Т. 44, № 1. – С. 156-177. DOI: 10.1177/0095327x16675965.
14. Jones E. Historical approaches to post-combat disorders. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. 2006. Vol. 361, no. 1468. P. 533-542. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2006.1814.
15. Morin R. The Difficult Transition from Military to Civilian Life [Електронний ресурс] / R. Morin // Pew. Research Center. – 2011. – Режим доступу: bit.ly/3PVzoQS.
16. Cornum R. Comprehensive Soldier Fitness. Building Resilience in a Challenging Institutional Context [Електронний ресурс] / R. Cornum, M. Matthews, M. Seligman // *American Psychologist*. – 2011. – Режим доступу: <https://www.apa.org/pubs/journals/releases/amp-66-1-4.pdf>.
17. Арешонков В.Ю. Цифровізація вищої освіти: виклики та відповіді / В.Ю. Арешонков // Вісник Національної академії педагогічних наук України. – 2020. – Т. 2, № 2. DOI: 10.37472/2707-305x-2020-2-2-13-2.
18. Buinytska O. Digitization of Higher Education Institution / O. Buinytska, L. Varchenko-Trotsenko, V. Hrytsehiak // *Educological discourse*. – 2020. – № 1. – С. 64-79. DOI: 10.28925/2312-5829.2020.1.6.
19. Особливості цифровізації освітнього процесу у вищій школі / Карплюк С.О. // Інформаційно-цифровий освітній простір України: трансформаційні процеси і перспективи розвитку. Матеріали методологічного семінару НАПН України. 4 квітня 2019 р. / За ред. В.Г. Кременя, О.І. Ляшенка; укл. А.В. Яцишин, О.М. Соколюк. – К, 2019. – 361 с. – С. 188-197.
20. Науково-методичне забезпечення цифровізації освіти України: стан, проблеми, перспективи [Електронний ресурс] / Василь Григорович Кремень [та ін.] // *Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine*. – 2022. – Т. 4, № 2. – С. 1-49. DOI: 10.37472/v.naes.2022.4223.
21. Mertala P. Paradoxes of participation in the digitalization of education: a narrative account. *Learning, Media and Technology*. 2019. Vol. 45, no. 2. P. 179-192. DOI: 10.1080/17439884.2020.1696362.
22. Schmidt J.T. Digitalization in Education: Challenges, Trends and Transformative Potential [Електронний ресурс] / Schmidt J.T., Tang M. // *Führen und Managen in der digitalen Transformation*. – 2020. – Wiesbaden, P. 287-312. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-28670-5_16.
23. Crittenden W.F. Embracing Digitalization: Student Learning and New Technologies [Електронний ресурс] / William F. Crittenden, Isabella K. Biel, William A. Lovely // *Journal of Marketing Education*. – 2018. – Т. 41, № 1. – С. 5-14. DOI: 10.1177/0273475318820895.
24. Кодекс законів про працю України [Електронний ресурс] // Офіційний вебпортал парламенту України. – Режим доступу: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/322-08#Text>.
25. Про затвердження Положення про Національну освітню електронну платформу [Електронний ресурс] // Офіційний вебпортал парламенту України. – Режим доступу: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0702-18#Text>.
26. Про затвердження Положення про електронний підручник [Електронний ресурс] // Офіційний вебпортал парламенту України. – Режим доступу: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0621-18#Text>.
27. Про затвердження Положення про електронні освітні ресурси [Електронний ресурс] // Офіційний вебпортал парламенту України. – Режим доступу: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z1695-12#Text>.
28. Мінцифри оприлюднює Рамку цифрової компетентності для громадян. [Електронний ресурс] // Офіційний вебпортал парламенту України. – Режим доступу: bit.ly/3LJFD0B.
29. Про Цілі сталого розвитку України на період до 2030 року [Електронний ресурс] // Офіційний вебпортал парламенту України. – Режим доступу: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/722/2019#Text>.

30. Міністерство освіти і науки України – Затверджені стандарти вищої освіти [Електронний ресурс] // Міністерство освіти і науки України. – Режим доступу: bit.ly/3PB3kAp.
31. Міністерство цифрової трансформації України [Електронний ресурс] // Міністерство цифрової трансформації України. – Режим доступу: <https://thedigital.gov.ua>.
32. Дія.Освіта [Електронний ресурс] // Дія.Освіта. – Режим доступу: <https://osvita.diiia.gov.ua>.
33. Міністерство соціальної політики України. Головна. [Електронний ресурс] // Міністерство соціальної політики України. – Режим доступу: <https://www.msp.gov.ua>.

Визнання:

UK-Ukraine twinning grants scheme – програма подвійних грантів (<https://www.twinningukraine.com>) для партнерства між Великою Британією та Україною у сфері наукових досліджень і розвитку, що фінансується Research England за підтримки Universities UK International та UK Research and Innovation. Координується Фондом Президента України з питань освіти, науки і спорту (<https://presidentfund.gov.ua>).

References:

1. Analytical Information According to the Ministry of Veterans Affairs of Ukraine. Ministry of Veterans Affairs of Ukraine. Retrieved from: <https://data.mva.gov.ua> [in Ukrainian].
2. Twentieth General National Survey. Veteran's Image in Ukrainian Society (14-16 January 2023). "Rating" Sociological group. Retrieved from: bit.ly/46n92wQ [in Ukrainian].
3. Krasylshchikov, A.L. (2005). Discharged Servicemen's Social Adaptation (Problems and Experience of Solving them in Ukraine and Foreign Countries). *Demography and social economy*, 2, 117-125 [in Ukrainian].
4. Abramov, E.V. (2016). Discharged Servicemen's Adaptation as a Tool to Ensure Their Competitiveness in the Labour Market. *Economics and Organization of Management*, 2 (22), 259-265 [in Ukrainian].
5. Buryak, O.O. & Hunevskiy, M.I. (2014). Social Adaptation of the Army of Ukraine in the New Conditions of Existence. *Scientific Works of Kharkiv National Air Force University*, 4(41), 160-166 [in Ukrainian].
6. Vdovychenko, T. (2017). Social and Professional Adaptation of Transferred to Reserve Military Servicemen as an Object of Financial Support. *World of Finance*, 1 (50), 166-180 [in Ukrainian].
7. Berezdetska, L. (2016). Peculiarities of Using State Programmes by Demobilized ATO Participants in Ukrainian society. *National Technical University of Ukraine Journal. Political science. Sociology. Law*, 1/2 (29-30), 30-38 [in Ukrainian].
8. Kharchenko, O., & Mramornova, O. (2016). The Anti-Terrorist Operation Veterans' Problems in the East of Ukraine, *Visnyk of V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University. Series "Sociological Studies of Contemporary society: Methodology, Theory, Methods"*, 37, 115-124 [in Ukrainian].
9. Psychological and Social Assistance through the ATO Veterans' Eyes (2016). "Reinassance" IBF, Psychological Crisis Service of Ukraine. Retrieved from: bit.ly/3tjQkYm [in Ukrainian].
10. Veterans Reintegration in Ukraine. National Survey (2022). Kyiv: IOM, Straight Together, Ministry of Veterans Affairs of Ukraine. Retrieved from: bit.ly/46qKh3f [in Ukrainian].
11. Elnitsky, C.A., Fisher, M.P., & Blevins, C.L. (2017). Military Service Member and Veteran Reintegration: A Conceptual Analysis, Unified Definition, and Key Domains. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00369 [in Ukrainian].
12. Terziev, V., & Dimitrova, S. (2014). A New View on Social Adaptation of the Military, Discharged from Military Service in Bulgaria. *European Scientific Journal*, vol. 2. Retrieved from: <https://ejournal.org/index.php/esj/article/viewFile/4792/4608> [in Ukrainian].
13. Cooper, L., Caddick, N., Godier, L., Cooper, A., & Fossey, M. (2016). Transition From the Military Into Civilian Life. *Armed Forces & Society*, 44 (1), 156-177. DOI: 10.1177/0095327x16675965 [in Ukrainian].
14. Jones, E. (2006). Historical approaches to post-combat disorders. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 361 (1468), 533-542. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2006.1814 [in Ukrainian].
15. Morin, R. (2011). The Difficult Transition from Military to Civilian Life. Pew. Research Center. Retrieved from: bit.ly/3PVzoQS [in Ukrainian].
16. Cornum, R, Matthews, M., & Seligman, M. (2011). Comprehensive Soldier Fitness. Building Resilience in a Challenging Institutional Context *American Psychologist*: Retrieved from: <https://www.apa.org/pubs/journals/releases/amp-66-1-4.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
17. Areshonkov, V.Yu. (2020). Digitalization of Higher Education: Challenges and Answers. *Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine. Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine*, 2(2). DOI: 10.37472/2707-305x-2020-2-2-13-2 [in Ukrainian].

18. Buinytska, O., Varchenko-Trotsenko, L., & Hrytseliak, B. (2020). Digitization of Higher Education Institution. *Educological discourse*, (1), 64-79. DOI: 10.28925/2312-5829.2020.1.6 [in Ukrainian].
19. Karpluk, S. (2019). Peculiarities of Educational Process Digitisation in Higher Education. In O. Kremen & O. Lyashenko (Eds.), *Information and Digital Educational Space of Ukraine: Transformational Processes and Development Prospects. Materials of the Methodological Seminar of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*. (A. Yatsyshyn & O. Sokolyuk, Comps.; pp. 188-197) [in Ukrainian].
20. Kremen, V.G., Bykov, V.Yu., Liashenko, O.I. et al. (2022). Scientific and Methodological Provision of Education Digitisation in Ukraine: Status, Problems, Prospects *Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine*, 4(2), 1-49. DOI: 10.37472/v.naes.2022.4223 [in Ukrainian].
21. Mertala, P. (2019). Paradoxes of participation in the digitalization of education: a narrative account. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 45(2), 179-192. DOI: 10.1080/17439884.2020.1696362 [in Ukrainian].
22. Schmidt, J.T., & Tang M. (2020). Digitalization in Education: Challenges, Trends and Transformative Potential. *Führen und Managen in der digitalen Transformation*. Wiesbaden, 287-312. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-28670-5_16 [in Ukrainian].
23. Crittenden, W.F., Biel, I.K., & Lovely, W.A. (2018). Embracing Digitalization: Student Learning and New Technologies. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 41(1), 5-14. DOI: 10.1177/0273475318820895 [in Ukrainian].
24. The Labour Code of Ukraine. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. Official Webportal. Retrieved from: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/322-08#Text> [in Ukrainian].
25. On the Approval of the Regulations on the National Educational Electronic Platform. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. Official Webportal. Retrieved from: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0702-18#Text> [in Ukrainian].
26. On the Approval of the Regulation on the Electronic Textbook. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. Official Webportal. Retrieved from: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0621-18#Text> [in Ukrainian].
27. On the Approval of the Regulation on Electronic Educational Resources. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. Official Webportal. Retrieved from: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z1695-12#Text> [in Ukrainian].
28. The Ministry of Digitisation Publishes the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens. Government Portal. Official Webportal. Retrieved from: bit.ly/3LJFDob [in Ukrainian].
29. About the Sustainable Development Goals of Ukraine for the Period until 2030. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. Official Webportal. Retrieved from: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/722/2019#Text> [in Ukrainian].
30. Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine – Approved Standards of Higher Education. Main page. Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. Retrieved from: bit.ly/3PB3kAp [in Ukrainian].
31. Diia. Education. Diia. Education. Retrieved from: <https://osvita.diia.gov.ua> [in Ukrainian].
32. Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine. Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine. Retrieved from: <https://thedigital.gov.ua> [in Ukrainian].
33. Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine. Main page. Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine. Retrieved from: <https://www.msp.gov.ua> [in Ukrainian].

Acknowledgment:

The UK-Ukraine R&I twinning grants scheme (<https://www.twinningukraine.com>) is a program aimed at fostering partnerships between the United Kingdom and Ukraine in the field of scientific research and development. This initiative is funded by Research England with the support of Universities UK International and UK Research and Innovation. The program is coordinated by the President of Ukraine's Fund for Education, Science, and Sports (<https://presidentfund.gov.ua>).

Посилання на статтю:

Balan O.S. *Digital Learning Tools as a Means of Ukrainian Veterans' Readaptation to Social Life* / O.S. Balan, M.Ye. Shepel, Ch. Morris // *Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал*. – 2023. – № 4 (68). – С. 5-18. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2023/No4/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.04.2023.1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10058126.

Reference a Journal Article:

Balan O.S. *Digital Learning Tools as a Means of Ukrainian Veterans' Readaptation to Social Life* / O.S. Balan, M.Ye. Shepel, Ch. Morris // *Economics: time realities. Scientific journal*. – 2023. – № 4 (68). – P. 5-18. – Retrieved from <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2023/No4/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.04.2023.1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10058126.

